

Experimental Study of Adaptive Loading in IM/DD OFDM Using In-band Optical Sub-Carrier SNR Monitoring

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Abstract: Subcarrier O-OFDM adaptive bit/power loading is achieved in an IM/DD system, with SNR measurements in the optical domain using high-resolution OSA. Experimental testbed results demonstrate good agreement with the DSP estimation at the receiver side.

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1. Introduction

Optical performance monitoring of signal quality is a key enabler of intelligent optical networks [1]. In fact, transmission impairments monitoring is needed at the nodes of the network, where traffic add/drop, routing and/or grooming processes are performed. There, optical cross-connects and reconfigurable optical add-drop multiplexers are configured/managed by a control plane, which requires in-band knowledge of the transmission impairments. This monitoring information is used for performing a suitable network resource allocation and management [2].

The advent of new and advanced optical modulation formats is attractive for improving the transmission performance. Precisely, optical orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (O-OFDM) has gained attention in optical communications, as it represents a promising candidate for high data rate optical systems and is suitable for future elastic and adaptive optical networks [3]. In these networks, the bandwidth and bit rate of the OFDM-based transceivers can be configured by the control layer, varying the electronic digital signal processing (DSP) of the transceiver and, thus, properly selecting the number of sub-carriers and the modulation format [3]. The overhead of information (including pilot tones and training symbols) allows monitoring system parameters for channel estimation and performance optimization [3]. However, this self-performance monitoring technique is implemented in the electrical domain, requiring an optical receiver front-end with the subsequent signal processing. For an appropriate network management, a simpler and non-intrusive signal quality monitoring per subcarrier is desirable also at the nodes of the network [1]. Thus, the control layer could dynamically reconfigure the parameters of each O-OFDM transceiver in order to overcome the signal degradation of specific subcarriers without the need of optical to electrical signal conversion. Among the DSP-based O-OFDM options, those based on intensity modulation and direct detection (IM/DD) represent a cost-effective solution for the implementation of bit-rate and bandwidth variable transceivers [3].

In this paper, subcarrier O-OFDM adaptive bit/power loading is achieved in an IM/DD system, employing signal to noise ratio (SNR) measurements using high-resolution optical spectrum analysis (OSA). A comparison with the digital signal processing at the receiver side for the SNR estimation is provided. Thanks to the correspondence between the two SNR measurement methods [1] a matching of the OFDM-based transceiver capacity and BER performance is experimentally demonstrated. This enables adaptive loading of the OFDM subcarriers with in-band optical SNR monitoring at any node of the network.

2. Experimental setup

The experimental set-up is described in Fig.1. The DSP and electrical up/downconversion at the transmitter/receiver are performed off-line, following the steps detailed in Fig.1. At the transmitter, randomly generated data are mapped into the corresponding constellation (ranging from BPSK up to 256 QAM). Adaptive bit/power loading is implemented using the rate adaptive version of the Levin-Campello algorithm [3]. Then, 4 training symbols are included every 100 OFDM frames. The resulting symbols feed an inverse fast Fourier transform (IFFT) of 512 subcarriers. Afterwards, a 2% cyclic prefix (CP) is added and the obtained OFDM symbols are then serialized. The digital OFDM signal, fixed to be running at 20Gbaud, is clipped and upconverted to an intermediate frequency of 10GHz by mixing with a digital oscillator. The resulting signal is converted to the analog domain by a digital to analog converter (DAC) at 64GSa/s. This analog signal is conditioned and injected to a Mach-Zehnder modulator (MZM) biased at the quadrature point and excited by a tunable laser source (TLS). After the MZM an optical filter, with 25GHz bandwidth centered at 1550.12nm, is placed in order to obtain an optical single sideband (SSB) signal.

The optical signal resulting from the transmitter is injected into the ADRENALINE testbed, whose simplified scheme is depicted in Fig.1. It is a basic 4-node photonic mesh network with amplified links of different lengths, ranging from 35km to 150km. In order to experimentally analyze the optical noise performance, a variable optical attenuator (VOA) is serially connected to an Erbium Doped Fiber Amplifier (EDFA) prior to the reception.

The spectral analysis is performed with a BOSA spectrum analyzer. The equipment performance is based on the use of stimulated Brillouin scattering (SBS) to obtain a narrow gain filter that can be used to scan the signal spectrum. The achieved spectral width with a SBS filter, when sweeping at a constant speed, can be as high as 10MHz at its full width half maximum, and 60MHz width at 40dB below the maximum response [4].

At the receiver, the incoming signal passes through an optical bandpass filter (OBPF) of 0.4nm and the resulting optical signal is detected by a PIN+TIA module. The detected current is then digitized by a real-time oscilloscope (OSC) running at 100GSa/s. The OFDM baseband signal is recovered after downconversion in the digital domain. The recovered signal is off-line demodulated, equalized and demapped.

Fig. 1. Experimental setup. DSP schemes of the transmitter (Tx DSP) and the receiver (Rx DSP). Inset shows the back-to-back power spectrum measured with BOSA.

3. Experimental results and discussion

The proposed procedure is tested at the variation of the optical signal to noise ratio (OSNR), with values ranging from 17.4dB up to 34.2dB, within a bandwidth of 0.1nm. As the resolution of the BOSA provides values of the power in a 0.08 pm bandwidth, the optical signal level measurement can be performed for each frequency component corresponding to the OFDM subcarriers. In fact, the spectrum is sliced in frequency intervals equivalent to the occupancy of each subcarrier, obtaining an individual performance monitoring of each subcarrier across the optical bandwidth. Regarding the noise level, it is also measured in those spectral intervals where there are no signal components, e.g. the edges of the optical signal. An important point is the fact that the response of the different optical/electrical components of the receiver is not ideal. Thus, before carrying out any measurement, a calibration is performed in order to find the linear transfer function between both domains: optical and electrical/digital [1]. The bit error ratio (BER) threshold has been set to $3 \cdot 10^{-3}$, assuming that it can be recovered after a hard decision forward error correction (HD-FEC) with only 7% overhead, as in [3].

Fig. 2. Back-to-back results. Capacity (left) and BER (right) as function of the overall OSNR and for the different SNR estimation methods.

First, a back to back case is measured and the achieved results are shown in Fig. 2. There, the maximum capacity of the IM/DD OFDM system and BER are plotted against the overall OSNR value for both subcarrier SNR measurement methods: either employing the BOSA or the DSP at the optical receiver (Rx) as in [1]. From the figures, we can observe that the measurement results are highly correlated as expected. In fact, the error in terms of capacity between the two methods ranges between 9.9% (20.8dB OSNR) and 0.5% (34.2dB OSNR), while maintaining the BER below the FEC threshold (maximum found at $2.7 \cdot 10^{-3}$).

Finally, the ADRENALINE testbed is configured in order to route the transmitted OFDM signal through different paths. Namely, the 50km and 150km paths are analyzed as depicted in Fig.1. The corresponding results at the variation of path/distance are depicted in Fig. 3. As expected, the maximum capacity is achieved for the back-to-back case. There we can observe that the overall maximum capacity difference between both methods ranges between 7% (~ 40 Gb/s after 50km) and 0.5% (~ 50 Gb/s in back-to-back) below the target BER. For the longest path the capacity difference is 1.3%, giving ~ 30 Gb/s below the FEC threshold.

Fig. 3. Experimental results when transmitting over the ADRENALINE testbed. Capacity (left) and BER (right) as function of the path distance and for the different SNR estimation methods.

4. Conclusions

Subcarrier IM/DD OFDM adaptive bit/power loading is demonstrated employing SNR measurements using high-resolution optical spectrum analysis. The proposed method features an error of less than 10% in terms of signal capacity. This enables the control layer to dynamically reconfigure the transceiver parameters at the OFDM subcarrier level in order to cope with signal degradation at the network nodes without the need of optical to electrical signal conversion.

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